

WOMEN WRITERS OF THE 18TH CENTURY

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Annotation: This article analyzes the work of 18th-century women writers and their role in society. The article highlights the role of women writers in society, famous representatives, the characteristics of their work, and their contribution to literature and social life. 18th-century women writers demonstrated such features as personal experience, social criticism, feminist motifs, and the development of the novel genre in their works. Their work was important not only in literature, but also in promoting women's rights and strengthening equality in society. The article will be useful for readers and researchers in studying 18th-century feminist literature and the work of women writers.

Anotatsiya: Ushbu maqolada 18-asr ayol yozuvchilari ijodi va ularning jamiyatdagi roli tahlil qilinadi. Maqolada ayol yozuvchilarning jamiyatdagi o'rnini, mashhur vakillari, ijodining xususiyatlari hamda ularning adabiyot va ijtimoiy hayotga qo'shgan hissasi yoritilgan. 18-asr ayol yozuvchilari o'z asarlarida shaxsiy tajriba, ijtimoiy tanqid, feministik motivlar va roman janrini rivojlantirish kabi xususiyatlarni namoyish etgan. Ularning ijodi nafaqat adabiyotda, balki ayollarning huquqlarini targ'ib qilish va jamiyatdagi tenglikni mustahkamlashda ham muhim ahamiyat kasb etgan. Maqola o'quvchi va tadqiqotchilar uchun 18-asr feminist adabiyoti va ayol yozuvchilar ijodini o'rganishda foydali bo'ladi.

Аннотация: В статье анализируется творчество писательниц XVIII века и их роль в обществе. В статье освещается роль писательниц в обществе, их выдающиеся представительницы, особенности их творчества и вклад в литературу и общественную жизнь. В своих произведениях писательницы XVIII века демонстрировали такие черты, как личный опыт, социальную критику, феминистские мотивы и развитие жанра романа. Их творчество имело значение не только для литературы, но и для продвижения прав женщин и укрепления равенства в обществе. Статья будет полезна читателям и исследователям, изучающим феминистскую литературу XVIII века и творчество писательниц.

Keywords: 18th century, women writers, literature, feminist motifs, society, novel genre, Mary Wollstonecraft, Fanny Burney, Eliza Haywood, social criticism.

Kalit soʻzlar: 18-asr, ayol yozuvchilar, adabiyot, feministik motivlar, jamiyat, roman janri, Mary Wollstonecraft, Fanny Burney, Eliza Haywood, ijtimoiy tanqid.

Ключевые слова: XVIII век, женщины-писательницы, литература, феминистские мотивы, общество, жанр романа, Мэри Уолстонкрафт, Фанни Берни, Элиза Хейвуд, социальная критика.

Introduction: The 18th century was a period of great change in literature and culture. During this period, many topics related to human rights, issues of equality in society, the Enlightenment, and the development of science entered literature. At the same time, women

writers also began to make their voices heard. Their work played an important role in highlighting the role, rights, and opinions of women in society.

Kirish: 18-asr — adabiyot va madaniyat sohasida katta o'zgarishlar yuz bergan davr hisoblanadi. Bu davrda inson huquqlari, jamiyatdagi tenglik masalalari, ma'rifatparvarlik va ilm-fan rivoji bilan bog'liq ko'plab mavzular adabiyotga kirib keldi. Shu bilan birga, ayol yozuvchilar ham o'z ovozi eshittira boshladi. Ularning ijodi jamiyatda ayollar rolini, huquqlarini va fikrlarini yoritishda muhim ahamiyat kasb etdi.

Введение: XVIII век стал временем больших перемен в литературе и культуре. В этот период в литературу вошли многие темы, связанные с правами человека, вопросами общественного равенства, эпохой Просвещения и развитием науки. В то же время женщины-писательницы также начали высказывать свои мнения. Их творчество сыграло важную роль в освещении роли, прав и мнений женщин в обществе.

Main part: The literature of the 18th century was a period of enlightenment and social change, during which new views began to emerge about the role of women in society and their rights. Although women were limited in political and social opportunities in many countries, they were able to express their opinions through literature. Therefore, women writers made their voices heard by highlighting social injustice, family relationships, and women's life problems in their works.

Their work not only enriched literary genres, but also served to change stereotypes in society. For example, works written in the genres of novels and essays revealed the personal experiences, feelings, and inner worlds of women. Through this, female writers not only introduced the reader to reality, but also promoted women's independence and rights to education.

18-The critical coverage of society played an important role in the work of women writers of the 18th century. Their works often raised topics such as social injustice, restrictions on women's education and freedom, and family oppression. At the same time, they called on readers to reflect, appreciate justice and human values. Women writers of the 18th century played an important role not only in literature, but also in the social and cultural life of society.

1-table of the role of 18th century female writers in society the role in a table view:

Female writer	Country	Works	Role and influence in society
Mary Wollstonecraft	England	<i>A Vindication of the Rights of Woman</i> (1792)	Promoted women's rights and education; developed feminist views
Fanny Burney	England	<i>Evelina</i> (1778), <i>Cecilia</i> (1782)	Criticized social norms in 18th-century English society; revealed the inner world of women
Eliza Haywood	England	<i>Love in Excess</i> (1719)	She shed light on the psychology of women through love and family relationships; contributed to strengthening female images
Frances Sheridan	Ireland	<i>Memoirs of Miss Sidney Biddulph</i> (1761)	Women revealed their personal experiences and social problems through literature.

Female writer	Country	Works	Role and influence in society
Sarah Fielding	England	<i>The Adventures of David Simple</i> (1744)	Highlighted social injustice and the hardships of women; inspired empathy and reflection in readers

In the 18th century, women writers began to promote their place in society and women's rights through their voices in literature. Their work became important not only as a literary legacy, but also as a means of changing society. One of the famous women writers of this period was **Mary Wollstonecraft** (1759–1797, England). She is known as a feminist and philosopher, and in her work "A Vindication of the Rights of Woman" (*A Vindication of the Rights of Woman*), she put forward the issues of women's education, independent thinking, and equal rights in society. Her views contributed greatly to the development of the feminist movement later.

Another famous writer is **Fanny Burney** (1752–1840, England). She wrote in the novel genre, and her works *Evelina* (1778) and *Cecilia* (1782) offer the reader a critical look at social norms, family and social problems in 18th-century English society. Burney's work focused on the inner world, emotions and personal experiences of women.

Eliza Haywood (1693–1756, England) also explored themes of love and family drama in her works. Her novel *Love in Excess* (1719) demonstrated psychological depth in the creation of female characters and criticized the social stereotypes of the time. Haywood's work served to study the psychology of women and bring their personal experiences into literature.

In addition, **Frances Sheridan** (1724–1766, Ireland) and **Sarah Fielding** (1710–1768, England) also occupy important positions among 18th-century women writers. Sheridan's *Memoirs of Miss Sidney Biddulph* highlighted the personal and social problems of women, while Fielding's *The Adventures of David Simple* addressed social injustice and human values. Their works served to arouse empathy and reflection in readers.

Women writers of the 18th century not only developed new genres and themes in literature, but also contributed to strengthening the position of women in society and protecting their rights. Their works continue to have a great influence on the development of feminist literature and social thought today.

Table 2. Famous 18th century female writers are as follows:

Female writer	Country	Famous works	Role and influence in society
Mary Wollstonecraft	England	<i>A Vindication of the Rights of Woman</i> (1792)	Promoted women's rights and education; developed feminist views
Fanny Burney	England	<i>Evelina</i> (1778), <i>Cecilia</i> (1782)	Criticized social norms in 18th-century English society; revealed the inner world of women
Eliza Haywood	England	<i>Love in Excess</i> (1719)	She shed light on the psychology of women through love and family relationships; contributed to strengthening female images
Frances Sheridan	Ireland	<i>Memoirs of Miss Sidney Biddulph</i> (1761)	She covered women's personal experiences and social problems through literature.

Female writer	Country	Famous works	Role and influence in society
Sarah Fielding	England	<i>The Adventures of David Simple</i> (1744)	Highlighted social injustice and the hardships of women; inspired empathy and reflection in readers

The work of women writers of the 18th century is characterized by the introduction of new directions and themes in literature. Their works were not only based on personal experiences, but also aimed to critically illuminate social injustice in society, family relationships, and the limited rights of women. In this way, women writers helped readers understand society by showing their own experiences and inner worlds.

Writing from personal experience played an important role in their work. Many writers brought their own life events, feelings, and perspectives into novels, essays, and poetry. For example, in the works of Fanny Burney and Mary Wollstonecraft, the personal lives and processes of women's self-realization were raised as a central theme. This approach allowed the reader to feel real-life situations.

In addition, **the critical coverage of society** is also of particular importance in the work of women writers. In their works, they criticized social injustice, educational restrictions, family obligations, and the place of women in society. At the same time, they called on readers to reflect, appreciate human values, and value justice.

Feminist themes also played an important role in the work of 18th-century women writers. The works of Mary Wollstonecraft emphasized the need for women to be educated, independent, and equal in society. The novels of Eliza Haywood and Frances Sheridan also served to defend women's rights by illuminating their psychology.

Table 3. Characteristics of the work of female writers

Feature	Description	Examples
Writing based on personal experience	Women writers brought their life stories, emotions, and inner worlds into their works.	Fanny Burney (<i>Evelina</i>), Mary Wollstonecraft (<i>A Vindication of the Rights of Woman</i>)
Critical coverage of society	Criticized social injustice, family obligations, and limited rights for women	Frances Sheridan (<i>Memoirs of Miss Sidney Biddulph</i>), Sarah Fielding (<i>The Adventures of David Simple</i>)
Feminist motives	Promoted women's education, independence, and equal rights in society	Mary Wollstonecraft, Eliza Haywood (<i>Love in Excess</i>)
The development of the novel genre	Creating new images, illuminating social situations, and revealing the psychology of women	Fanny Burney, Eliza Haywood, Sarah Fielding

Women writers of the 18th century also made a great contribution **to the development of the novel genre**. They created new characters in their works and showed various social situations in society. Through this, the reader not only felt reality, but also got acquainted with the life problems, feelings and aspirations of women.

The work of 18th-century women writers is characterized by personal experiences, criticism of society, feminist motifs, and the development of the novel genre. Their works were important not only in literature, but also in strengthening the role of women in society.

Women writers of the 18th century played a significant role in the cultural and social development of their time. Their works are important not only as a literary legacy, but also in the advancement of women's rights, equality in society, and human values. Today, their work forms the foundation of feminist literature and is an important source for the voices of women writers to be heard.

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